

EFFECT OF PRUNING, ORGANIC AND INORGANIC NUTRITION ON SOIL PROPERTIES OF MANGO (*Mangifera indica* L.)

CV. AMRAPALI FIELD

Dileep Kumar Tiwari*, Srikant*, Harikesh** and Bhanu Pratap*

*Department of Horticulture

**Department of Agronomy

Narendra Deva University of Agriculture & Technology,

Kumarganj, Ayodhya-224 229 (U.P.)

Harikeshkumarup@gmail.Com

(MS Received: 05.02.2024; MS Revised:07.03.2024; MS Accepted:08.03.2024)

MS 3186

(RESEARCH PAPER IN HORTICULTURE,)

Abstract

The present study was conducted to evaluate the "Effect of pruning, organic and inorganic nutrition on soil properties of mango (*Mangifera indica* L.) cv. Amrapali field. was carried out at Main Experiment Station, Department of Horticulture, Narendra Deva University of Agriculture and Technology, Kumarganj, Ayodhya (U.P.) during the years 2015-16 and 2016-17. The experiments were conducted in Randomized Block Design with ten treatments and three replications. The detail of treatments were as T₁-5 cm pruning+FYM@ 20 kg per plant, T₂-5 cm pruning+ Vermicompost @ 10kg per plant, T₃-5 cm pruning+ ZnSO₄ @ 1.0 % + Borax @ 0.4%, T₄-10 cm pruning+ FYM@ 20kg+ Zinc sulphate@ 1.0% per plant, T₅-10 cm pruning+ Vermicompost @10kg+ Borax @0.4% per plant, T₆-10 cm pruning+PSB 250g+ MgSO₄ @0.5% per plant, T₇-15 cm pruning+FYM @20kg+ Zinc sulphate @1.0% per plant, T₈-15 cm pruning+ Vermicompost @10kg+ Borax@0.4% per plant, T₉-15 cm pruning+ PSB 250g+ MgSO₄ @0.5% per plant, T₁₀- Control (no pruning+ water spray). The maximum buildup of organic carbon content (0.40 and 0.41 gkg⁻¹), maximum reduction in EC (0.33 and 0.31 dSm⁻¹), and maximum reduction in soil pH (8.31 and 8.30) was obtained with in the treatment T₈ (15 cm pruning + Vermicompost @10kg+ Borax @ 0.4 %).

Key word- pruning, organic and inorganic nutrition, soil properties, mango field

Introduction

Mango (*Mangifera indica* L.) is the fifth most important fruit of the world after apple, citrus, banana and grape. It is cultivated in more than 100 countries because of its delicious taste, excellent flavour, attractive fragrance and excellent source of vitamin A (1400 IU) and C. The total annual production of mango in India is 18.43 million tonnes, cultivated in 2.52 million hectare with productivity (7.30 Mt/ ha), (Anonymous, 2016). The major mango producing states in India are Uttar Pradesh (4.30 million tonne) followed by Andhra Pradesh (2.74 million tonnes), and Karnataka (1.75 million tonnes). Considering the importance of mango there is dire need to initiate the nutrient management and pruning intensity programme to increase vegetative growth, fruit size, uniform ripening, fruit yield and quality of mango. In addition to nutrient intensity and pruning has also been reported to manage plant canopy and enhance the flowering, fruiting, yield and quality of many fruit crops (Ali *et al.*, 2001).

Generally Indian soil is deficient to N and P. Nitrogen is one of the most important essential plant nutrients. It is constituents of protoplasm, protein, chlorophyll, nucleotide, alkaloids, hormones and vitamins, which play an important role in crop production and awareness on health security with use of natural food. Organic food and quality produce, the judicious use of chemicals is gaining less importance and banned by few countries. The use of chemical fertilizers for production of herbal drugs is also advisable to maintain the quality and medicinal properties of herbal species. It requires favorable soil and climate condition for properly development of plant. The yield and quality of herbs is highly affected by agro-cultural practices. In most of the Horticultural, Medicinal and Vegetable crops, FYM is the most common organic manure used for supplement the initial requirement of nutrients for better establishment such as animal, plant wastage i.e. Nitrogen, Phosphorus, Potash and micronutrients. The continuous application of huge amount of chemical fertilizers hamper the fruit quality, soil health and generate pollution. The combination of organic and in-organic nutrients paves away to overcome of these problems. Plant nutrient can be supplied from different sources viz., organic manures and chemical fertilizers for better utilization of resources and to produce crop with less expenditure. Organic manures enhance nutrient availability in order to improve the soil health, soil structure and provide conducive environment for the treatment of soil micro

flora. Potentially of using organic manures along with balanced fertilizers are well established in increasing crop yield and sustained crop production (Nambiar and Abrol, 1992).

The micro-nutrients play vital role in growth, development, retention and quality of fruits. The foliar feeding of micro-nutrients has gained much importance in recent years and comparatively more effective for rapid recovery of plants, as under high soil pH conditions, most of macro and micro-nutrients are unavailable. Various trials have been conducted on foliar feeding of micro-nutrients in different fruit crops and found effective in improving the vegetative growth, yield and quality of fruits (Sindhu *et al.*, 1994; Banik *et al.*, 1997 and Babu and Singh, 1998).

It is therefore, necessary to standardize possible pruning intensity in combination with sources of nutrients to a specific soil and agro-climatic condition for better plant growth, production and quality of mango.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was carried out on 25 year old mango orchard planted under sodic soil condition and site is located at Main Experiment Station, Horticulture, Narendra Deva University of Agriculture and Technology, Kumarganj, Faizabad on the Raebareli road at the distance of 42 km away from Ayodhya district head quarter. Geographically it is situated at 26^o-47^oN latitude, 82.12^oE longitude of 113 meter away from mean sea level. This site is located in typical saline-alkaline belt of indigenous plains of eastern Uttar Pradesh. The experiment was laid out in Randomized Block Design with 3 replications. One plant was taken as unit per plot in the treatment. The detail of treatments were as T₁-5 cm pruning+FYM@ 20 kg per plant, T₂-5 cm pruning+ Vermicompost @ 10kg per plant, T₃-5 cm pruning+ ZnSO₄ @ 1.0 % + Borax @ 0.4%, T₄-10 cm pruning+ FYM@ 20kg+ Zinc sulphate@ 1.0% per plant, T₅-10 cm pruning+ Vermicompost @10kg+ Borax @0.4% per plant, T₆-10 cm pruning+PSB 250g+ MgSO₄ @0.5% per plant, T₇-15 cm pruning+FYM @20kg+ Zinc sulphate @1.0% per plant, T₈-15 cm pruning+ Vermicompost @10kg+ Borax@0.4% per plant, T₉-15 cm pruning+ PSB 250g+ MgSO₄ @0.5% per plant, T₁₀- Control (no pruning+ water spray). The soil characteristics parameters were recorded as following.

S.No.	Chemical properties	Method employed
1.	Soil reaction (pH)	1:2.5 soil water suspension by using glass electrode pH meter (Jackson, 1967)
2.	Electrical Conductivity (dSm ⁻¹)	Electrical conductivity bridge (1:2.5 soil water suspension)
3.	Organic carbon (g kg ⁻¹)	Walkley and Black rapid titration method (Walkley and Black, 1934)

Results and Discussion

The maximum buildup of organic carbon content (0.40 and 0.41 gkg⁻¹) was observed with the application of treatment T₈ (15 cm pruning + Vermicompost @10kg+ Borax @ 0.4 %) during both years (2015-16 and 2016-17), respectively. While, minimum buildup was obtained (0.37 and 0.38 gkg⁻¹) in the treatment T₁₀ (Control). It is also clear from the data the buildup in organic carbon was increased in the next year of the experimentation. This was due to vermicompost application. Vermicompost released organic acid and other microbial products during decomposition which ultimately increase the organic matter content of the soil. Similar result also obtained by Dey and Nath (2015) in cabbage field.

The maximum reduction in EC (0.33 and 0.31 dSm⁻¹) was obtained with in treatment T₈ (15 cm pruning + Vermicompost @10kg+ Borax @ 0.4 %) and minimum reduction (0.38 and 0.36 dSm⁻¹) was obtained with in the treatment T₁₀ (Control). The results are conformed with findings of Azarmi *et al.* (2018) in tomato field. The maximum reduction in soil pH 8.31 and 8.30 was obtained with in the treatment T₈ (15 cm pruning + Vermicompost @10kg+ Borax @ 0.4 %) and minimum reduction was (8.71 and 8.70) obtained with in the treatment T₁ (Control). Same trend was also obtained during the both year of experimentation. Atiyeh *et al.* (2001) and Azarmi *et al.* (2018) reported that the increase of vermicompost rate in the soil resulted in the decrease in soil pH.

References

1. Atiyeh, R.M.; Lee Edward, C.A.; Sulbar, S. and Metzger T. (2001). Pig manure vermicompost as a component of a Horticultural bedding plant medium, Effect on physiochemical properties and plant growth. *Bioresour technol* 78:11-20
2. Ali, H.S.; Ghaffor, A.; Waseem, K. and Nadeem, M.A. (2001). Growth and yield response of phalsa (*Grewia asiatica* L.) to various pruning intensities and dates. *Journal of Biological Sciences*, 1 (7) : 548-550.
3. Azarmi, R.; Giglou, M.T. and Taleshnikail, R.D. (2018). Influence of vermicompost on soil chemical and physical properties in tomato field. *African J. Biotech.*, 7(14):2397-2401
4. Babu, N. and Singh, A.R. (1998). Effect of boron, zinc and copper sprays on growth and development of litchi fruits. *Punjab Hort. J.* 34 (3-4) : 75-79.
5. Banik, B.C. and S. K. Sen (1997). Effect of three levels of zinc iron. Boron and their interactions on growth, flowering and yield of mango cv. Fazli. *Hort. Journal*; 10 (1): 23-29.
6. Dhube S. B.*, S. H. Kamble, R. D. Shelke, P.B. Dongare, 2023, Cost, Returns And Profitability In Organic And Inorganic Soybean Production In Wardha District (M. S.) Vol. Xii, Issue Xxxv, Jan 2023 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601, Pp 454-456.
7. Nambiar, K.K.M. and Abrol, I.P. (1992). Long term fertilizer experiment in India: An overview. *Fertilizer News*, 34 (4): 11-26
8. Sindhu, P.C.; V.P. Ahlawat and A.S. Nain (1994). Effect of foliar spray of zinc sulphate on total soluble solids and acidity percentage of grapes cv. Perlette, Res. Bull. CCSHAU Hissar.
9. S.S. Shilewant1, And V.D. Patil2 2020, Effect Of Soil And Foliar Feeding Of Nutrients Through Organic And Inorganic Sources On Yield And Quality Of Sweet Orange (*Citrus Sinensis* L. Osbeck) Vol. IX, Issue Xxxii, Jan 2020 Multilogic In Science, Pp 443-345.

10. Sukirti Mohanty1*, Ashok Kumar Paikaray2, Ruchita Panda 2022, Effect Of Organic And Inorganic Sources Of Nitrogen On Flowering Characteristics And Shelf Life Of Tuberose (*Polianthes Tuberosa* L.) Cv. Prajwal, Vol. Xii, Issue Xxxiii, July 2022 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601, Pp 182-185.
11. Jackson, M.L. (1967). Soil chemical analysis, prentice Hall of India, Pvt. Ltd, New Delhi.
12. Walkley, A. and Black, J.A. (1934). An examination of Degtzariff method for determination of soil organic matter and proposed modification of chromic acid titration method. *Soil Sci.* 37 (6): 29-38.

Table Effect of pruning, organic and inorganic nutrition on OC and EC in mango cv. Amrapali.

Treatments		OC (gkg ⁻¹)		EC (dSm ⁻¹)	
		2015-16	2016-17	2015-16	2016-17
T ₁	5 cm pruning + FYM @ 20 kg per plant	0.37	0.38	0.37	0.35
T ₂	5 cm pruning + Vermicompost @ 10 kg per plant	0.39	0.40	0.34	0.32
T ₃	5 cm pruning + ZnSO ₄ @ 1.0 % + Borax @ 0.4%	0.37	0.38	0.37	0.35
T ₄	10 cm pruning + FYM @ 20kg + Zinc Sulphate @ 1.0% per plant	0.39	0.40	0.35	0.33
T ₅	10 cm pruning + Vermicompost @ 10 kg + Borax @ 0.4% per plant	0.39	0.40	0.34	0.32
T ₆	10 cm pruning + PSB 250g + MgSO ₄ @ 0.5% per plant	0.38	0.39	0.35	0.33
T ₇	15 cm pruning + FYM @ 20kg + Zinc Sulphate @ 1.0% per plant	0.38	0.39	0.35	0.33
T ₈	15 cm pruning + Vermicompost @ 10 kg + Borax @ 0.4% per plant	0.40	0.41	0.33	0.31
T ₉	15 cm pruning + PSB 250g + MgSO ₄ @ 0.5% per plant	0.37	0.38	0.36	0.34
T ₁₀	Control (no pruning + water spray)	0.37	0.38	0.38	0.36
SEm±		0.007	0.006	0.008	0.006
CD at 5%		0.02	0.019	0.022	0.017

Table Effect of pruning, organic and inorganic nutrition pH after harvest in mango cv. Amrapali

Treatments		soil pH	
		2015-16	2016-17
T ₁	5 cm pruning + FYM @ 20 kg per plant	8.71	8.70
T ₂	5 cm pruning + Vermicompost @ 10 kg per plant	8.61	8.60
T ₃	5 cm pruning + ZnSO ₄ @ 1.0 % + Borax @ 0.4%	8.69	8.68
T ₄	10 cm pruning + FYM @ 20kg + Zinc Sulphate @ 1.0% per plant	8.66	8.65
T ₅	10 cm pruning + Vermicompost @ 10 kg + Borax @ 0.4% per plant	8.51	8.50
T ₆	10 cm pruning + PSB 250g + MgSO ₄ @ 0.5% per plant	8.36	8.35
T ₇	15 cm pruning + FYM @ 20kg + Zinc Sulphate @ 1.0% per plant	8.41	8.40
T ₈	15 cm pruning + Vermicompost @ 10 kg + Borax @ 0.4% per plant	8.31	8.30
T ₉	15 cm pruning + PSB 250g + MgSO ₄ @ 0.5% per plant	8.51	8.50
T ₁₀	Control (no pruning + water spray)	8.71	8.70
SEm±		0.141	0.140
CD at 5%		NS	NS